

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)
Volume I, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication
ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060
Publisher: Binas Publishing
Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DR. NOVA MARIE ENTRINA ANTIQUANDO

Instructor III

Negros Oriental State University – Guihulngan City
Campus (NORSU-G)

my.supernova84@gmail.com

“MEMORIES OF YESTERDAY”

The scent of sadness crawls within me,
As I stumble upon a familiar face;
Seeing a silhouette of you in a corner,
Ignites moments that we've been together.

Your coming to me created a vibrant yesterday,
The grey skies softened and colors bloomed greatly;
My empty emotions became saturated gradually,
That no other person has brought such happiness warmly.

In your presence, I found calmness,
Even during my turbulent moments;
You acted as a gentle transition,
And you were my haven through the storm.

Each moment we carved together
Dances across the realm we built as shelter;
Dwelling in the deep and hollow places in my heart,
Pressed as footprints scattered in the sand.

With you, everything seemed majestic
Your name is quietly and silently whispered;
My dreams depicted your unique existence
Even just in brief moments.

And though the seasons shift,
The days of yesterday seem like a faded melody;
But stronger now to face the future and today,

For our love are just memories of yesterday.

